

Ammonium arylthiocarbamate : The compounds were prepared by the reported method⁶.

S-(2-Acetyl-amino-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazolyl)-N-arylthiocarbamates (3) : A mixture of 2-chloro-acetamido-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (0.01 mol) and ammonium arylthiocarbamate (0.01 mol) in dry acetone was stirred for 0.5 h at room temperature and then refluxed for 90 min. Excess of solvent was then distilled off, the solid product washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

Pharmacological screening : The compounds were screened for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. Representative compounds were screened for antitubercular activity against the human virulent strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (H₃₇R_v).

Results and Discussion

Antibacterial activity : Out of fifteen compounds, seven compounds were found to be active against *S. aureus* and eight compounds active against *E. coli*; and five compounds active against both the species. Compound having 4-chloro substitution was most active against both the species. Moreover, compounds having 4-methyl, 4-methoxy, 4-ethoxy and 3-nitro substitutions were also active against both the species but their activity being low this details of biological activity are not reported.

Antitubercular activity : The compounds showed poor antitubercular activity. Out of five compounds, not a single compound was effective at lower concentration (35 µg ml⁻¹). But two compounds, having 2,3-dimethyl and 3-nitro substitutions were found effective at higher concentration (Table 1).

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY DATA OF 1,3,4-OXADIAZOLES

Sl. no.	R	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	2-OH ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₃ S	162	52
2.	3-OH ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₃ S	144	52
3.	4-OH ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₃ S	196	50
4.	2-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₃ S	142	59
5.	3-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₃ S	166	54
6.	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₃ S	127	56
7.	2,3-(OH) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₃ S	136	47
8.	2,4-(OH) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₃ S	145	56
9.	2-O ₂ C ₂ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₄ S	136	54
10.	4-O ₂ C ₂ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₄ S	117	52
11.	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ O ₃ S	166	57
12.	3-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ O ₃ S	128	61
13.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ O ₃ S	106	59
14.	2-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₃ S	140	64
15.	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₃ S	151	61

*N and S analyses found satisfactory.

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Synthesis of 2-(2-Amino-3-pyridyl)-3-substituted-benzoylamino-4-thiazolidinones

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4-THIAZOLIDINONE derivatives are known to possess a variety of physiological properties¹. These reports prompted us to synthesise a series of hitherto unreported 2-(2-amino-3-pyridyl)-3-substituted-benzoylamino-4-thiazolidinones.

The required 2-aminonicotinaldehyde hydrazones (3) were prepared by the condensation of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde (1) with aromatic acid hydrazides (2) in ethanol in the presence of a few drops of glacial acetic acid². The cyclocondensation of thioglycolic acid with these hydrazones led to the formation of 2-(2-amino-3-pyridyl)-3-substituted-benzoylamino-4-thiazolidinones (4) in DMF containing anhydrous ZnCl₂ (Scheme 1). The structures of the compounds were determined by elemental analyses and ir spectral data. The ir spectra of 4 exhibited characteristic bands at 3 430 (NH), 2 930

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF 2-(2-AMINO-3-PYRIDYL)-3-SUBSTITUTED-BENZOYLAMINO-4-THIAZOLIDINONES (4)*

Sl. no.	Ar	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)	
				N	S
1.	Phenyl	55	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	17.76 (17.83)	10.07 (10.19)
2.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	65	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	17.21 (17.07)	9.61 (9.76)
3.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	66	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	16.16 (16.28)	9.22 (9.30)
4.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	62	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂ SOl	16.22 (16.09)	9.05 (9.20)
5.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂ SOl	16.21 (16.09)	9.04 (9.20)
6.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	70	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂ SOl	16.23 (16.09)	9.00 (9.20)
7.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	58	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	16.88 (16.97)	9.60 (9.70)
8.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	16.82 (16.97)	9.62 (9.70)
9.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	50	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₄ S	19.41 (19.50)	8.82 (8.91)
10.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	55	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₄ S	19.40 (19.50)	8.80 (8.91)
11.	3-Pyridyl	60	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₅ O ₂ S	22.10 (22.22)	10.05 (10.16)
12.	4-Pyridyl	62	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₅ O ₂ S	22.11 (22.22)	10.06 (10.16)

*All compounds have m.p. >300°, and satisfactory C and H analyses were obtained.

(CH₂), 1 720 (C=O, thiazolidinone), 1 610 (CONH) and 1 320 and 1 230 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C). The spectra also showed bands at 1 525, 1 460, 1 380, 1 110, 1 080, 970, 910, 880, 790 and 750 cm⁻¹. The mass

spectra of 4 (Ar=C₆H₅ and *p*-CH₃.C₆H₄) showed strong M⁺ peaks at m/z 314 and 328, respectively.

Experimental

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 283 spectrophotometer. Melting points were taken in sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. The physical and analytical data are presented in Table 1.

2-(2-Amino-3-pyridyl)-3-substituted-benzoylamino-4-thiazolidinones (4): Appropriate 2-aminonicotinaldehyde hydrazone (3; 0.01 mol) was refluxed in DMF (25 ml) containing a pinch of anhydrous ZnCl₂ and thioglycolic acid (0.01 mol) for 8 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and poured into ice-cold water. The resulting solid was filtered and washed several times with water and then recrystallised from DMF-water to give 4.

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Preparation and Comparative Studies of some Substituted 4-Thiazolidinones and 2-Azetidinones linked to 1,3,4-Thiadiazole

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4-THIAZOLIDINONE derivatives have been found to possess wide variety of biological activities^{1,2}. 2-Azetidinone and its derivatives also possess wide therapeutic activities³. With a view to get better therapeutic agents, we have undertaken the preparation of 4-thiazolidinone and 2-azetidinone derivatives.

Experimental

Melting points of the compound were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and uv spectra (MeOH) on a Perkin-Elmer 202 spectrophotometer.

2,5-Diaminothiadiazole¹ and 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone/benzophenone⁴ were prepared by the reported methods.

2,5-Bis(α-methyl-2'-hydroxy-5'-methylbenzal-amino)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (1a): A mixture of 2,5-diamino-1,3,4-thiadiazole and 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone taken 1 : 2 molar ratio in ethanol was refluxed for 2 h. The product thus separated was worked up as usual and crystallised from ethanol, (65%), m.p. 210° (Found: C, 63.01; H, 5.20; N, 14.70. C₂₀H₂₀N₄O₂S requires: C, 63.16; H, 5.26; N, 14.74%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 200 (bonded OH), 1 670 (N=C) and 1 435, 1 350, 1 195 cm⁻¹ (1,3,4-thiadiazole ring); λ_{max} (MeOH) 262 (log ε 3.65), 315 (3.34) and 365 (3.37).

Similarly, other substituted Schiff bases were prepared (Table 1).

2,5-Bis(α-methyl-2'-(2"-hydroxy-5"-methyl)-5'-H-4'-thiazolidinone-3'-yl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (2a): A mixture of 1a (0.01 mol) in benzene was refluxed with thioglycolic acid (0.02 mol) on a water-bath for 4 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to get 2a, (53%), m.p. 220° (Found: C,

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF SCHIFF BASES (1)*

Sl. no.	R	R'	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	CH ₃	H	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂	210	65
2.	CH ₃	NO ₂	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂	230	60
3.	CH ₃	Br	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂	201	70
4.	C ₆ H ₅	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂	190	67
5.	C ₆ H ₅	NO ₂	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂	185	78
6.	C ₆ H ₅	Br	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂	165	75

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

54.50; H, 4.49; N, 10.57. C₂₀H₁₈N₄O₂S requires: C, 54.58; H, 4.54; N, 10.57%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 101 (CH), 1 605 (N-C) 1 440, 1 360 and 1 180 (1,3,4-thiadiazole ring) and 1 735 strong (C=O) for thiazolidinone ring system); λ_{max} (MeOH) 270 (log ε 3.40), 330 (3.14) and 380 (3.45).

Similarly, other substituted 4-thiazolidinone derivatives were prepared (Table 2).

2,5-Bis(α-methyl-2'-(2"-hydroxy-5"-methyl)-5'-methyl-4'-thiazolidinone-3'-yl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (3a): Thiolic acid (0.02 mol) added to a saturated solution of the Schiff base (1a; 0.01 mol) in dry benzene (50 ml) was refluxed for 8 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol as brown needles (3a; 50%), m.p. 205° (Found: C, 56.05; H, 5.00; N, 10.01. C₂₆H₂₆O₄S₂ requires: C, 56.11; H, 5.03; N, 10.07%); ν_{max} (KBr), 3 050 (OH), 1 615 (N-C), 1 422, 1 365 and 1 190 (1,3,4-thiadiazole ring system), 1 760 and 1 782 cm⁻¹ (C=O of thiazolidinone ring system); λ_{max} (MeOH) 261 (log ε 3.14), 327 (3.34) and 375 (3.50).

Similarly, other substituted 4-thiazolidinone derivatives were prepared (Table 2).

2,5-Bis(α-methyl-2'-(2"-hydroxy-5"-methyl)-5'-carboxymethyl-4'-thiazolidinone-3'-yl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole: 1a (0.01 mol) was condensed with thiomalic acid